

Scientists: the Green Deal needs to be urgently revived

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Dear Policymakers,

We are in an unprecedented state of planetary crisis, risking the livelihoods of millions of people in Europe, and billions globally. The European Green Deal, in its original form, was poised to set ambitious steps for tackling these crises and addressing key societal challenges. However, the Green Deal is presently going through a continuous path of weakening, as elements of it are being lost or replaced in the policy process. As scientists, we are particularly concerned about a series of unjustified, poorly informed and rushed deregulations which fail to align with the dire need for transformative changes toward sustainability. The first set of decisions already taken by the new Commission, as well as propositions and decisions made by the Parliament, mark worrying signs of poor environmental commitment and poor understanding of the associated risks. We therefore urge the new Commission, the Parliament and EU Member States to urgently rethink their strategy around the Green Deal, to reinstate its ambition, and ensure its proper implementation.

Why are we concerned?

Over the course of 2023 and 2024, the European Commission has taken a series of contested decisions, especially on the Common Agricultural Policy (**CAP**) and Sustainable Use of

Pesticides' Regulation (**SUR**) (see above) - which the new Commission has not expressed an intention to reverse. We are concerned to see that the new Commission has already taken decisions that show poor environmental commitment, with proposals to delay and amend the EU Deforestation Regulation (**EUDR**), as well as the intentions to alter the Habitat Directive and the **conservation status of species**, such as wolves.

While the new Commission expressed a general commitment to the Green Deal, and the ambition to ensure the success of the Nature Restoration Law, we are witnessing an alarming shift in the overall policy language, motivation and priorities. Instead of sustainability, the new focus of the Commission is on 'competitiveness', 'productivity' and 'economic growth', while ignoring the planetary boundaries or safe limits for humanity set by Earth's conditions. This is evident in the Strategy outlined for the Commission's first 100 days, which made no mention of biodiversity. It is essential to acknowledge, however, that both our economy and our wellbeing are intrinsically linked to Earth's resources and the state of our environment.

With the present letter, representing a collaborative and voluntary effort from members of the scientific community across disciplines, we express our growing and grave concerns about the new direction taken by the Commission regarding the Green Deal. The decisions towards industrial competitiveness and deregulation seriously undermine the actions needed to achieve carbon neutrality, halt biodiversity loss, and address health impacts of excessive environmental pollution. Scientists have been expressing their concerns about these developments through various channels, such as the [Europe for Nature initiative](#) and an [open letter](#) published in June 2024. We feel that the raised concerns and warnings have not been taken seriously, and instead the rollback of the Green Deal continues. We thus strongly recommend adhering to the **principles of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union** (TFEU), especially the legal duty to protect human and environmental health following the precautionary principle (TFEU Article 191), the duty to care with regard to health risks (TFEU Article 168), and the obligation to comply with international agreements (e.g. Article 105). In the following text, we justify our concerns in more detail.

1) **Downgrading of the European Deforestation Regulation (EUDR)**

The recent amendments to the EUDR are a concerning step backward from the planned EU efforts to halt global deforestation by tracing and ensuring that specific commodity products do not come from deforested land - as critical means to address both biodiversity and climate targets. The suggested delay in its implementation penalises companies that have already invested to be ready on time, while rewarding those conducting 'business as usual'. The EU Parliament proposed additional amendments that would have severely undermined the core goal of the EUDR to address European supply chain impacts on deforestation and forest degradation. Particularly, the proposals to add a "no risk" category, and to adopt forest definitions that do not align with science, would have risked emptying the EUDR from its objectives. While we are relieved to see that the European Council rejected these additional amendments, the delay in EUDR's implementation is still a major weakness.

2) **Continuity of the pre-election line regarding the SUR, CAP and RES**

Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR)

The Commission's original SUR proposal was aligned with strong evidence of the broad and increasing prevalence of agrochemicals in our food and water and the associated negative impacts these chemicals have on human health and the environment. The SUR would have been a powerful instrument, to finally introduce, for the first time, concrete EU-wide targets for pesticide reduction. Yet even after repeated weakening, the SUR was rejected by the European Parliament and subsequently withdrawn by the Commission. In doing so, they ignored an evidence-based [open letter signed by 6000 scientists](#) and an [appeal from over 1 million citizens](#) in favour of the SUR. On the other hand, the new Commission welcomed the outcomes of the EU's Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture - which highlights (again) the need to secure healthy food to European citizens. Without revising and re-tabling the SUR, it is hard to imagine how the Commission envisions implementing the recommendation which they cordially endorsed.

Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

Both the Parliament and Council voted for a [Commission proposal](#) that weakened the environmental effectiveness of five out of nine basic CAP environmental standards, presumably to enhance production and yields. This includes eliminating fallow land on arable land and enhancing the possibilities to convert permanent grassland into arable land. There is no evidence that these decisions have addressed the core issues for farmers - while in the longer term, they may well increase the risks to farming and food security by accelerating environmental degradation (soil erosion, flood and fire risks, nutrient loss, greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity loss).

Renewable Energy Sources (RES)

The REPower EU plan prioritises renewable energy (RES) as an overriding public interest and designates 'go-to' areas with less demanding environmental regulations. However, rapid RES expansion, without careful consideration of trade-offs with other objectives, risks land and water industrialization, habitat and soil degradation, and possible reduction of food production and biodiversity conservation, contradicting the EU Soil Strategy and the upcoming Soil Monitoring Law aimed at "no-net land take" by 2050. Uncontrolled RES expansion also weakens the procedural safeguards of Appropriate Assessments under the Habitats and Birds Directives, challenging also the EU's biodiversity commitments in TFEU Article 191. Instead, RES expansion needs to enshrine biodiversity-inclusive integrated spatial planning at the EU member state level, as a means to identify and designate any further areas for expansion - in alignment with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework Target 1 and 3.

3) Strong signals of the new Commission and Parliament showing low ambition and weak commitment to environmental standards, regulations, and science-based strategies

Several recent decisions and dialogues have signalled a worrying shift toward lower environmental ambitions. The rollback of **pesticide reduction targets** (see below) and delays in the **'Fit for 55'** package reflect a growing prioritisation of short-term vested economic interests over long-term sustainability for humans, the environment and the economy, based on unsubstantiated claims regarding food security. This new direction not only undermines the aims of the Green Deal but also contradicts the EU's commitments to reduce and reverse

biodiversity loss made under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Furthermore, the proposal to **downgrade the protection status of wolves** (and other species), raises concerns that such actions would weaken both the Habitats Directive and the EU's alignment with international agreements like the Bern Convention, threatening those essential environmental policy instruments. Most importantly, it indicates that the Commission neither supports nor considers the much-needed science-based policy decisions as European citizens confront unprecedented climate and environmental challenges.

An overall rollback

Altogether, recent decisions and current political processes **represent an overall course of rollback of environmental standards and regulations**, some of which have been the outcome of decades of efforts strongly backed-up by science and society. Environmental regulations are being delayed, watered down, or even dropped completely (e.g. SUR) - and other elements of the Green Deal seem to have been removed from the table (Sustainable Food Systems' Framework). Such actions undermine trust in the EU's environmental commitments and hinder much needed efforts to address the biodiversity and climate crises and the resilience of our ecosystems and societies, as well as risks to our economy and wellbeing.

This departure from the initial transformative spirit of the Green Deal seems to prevail in many current EU decisions and this is worrying for several reasons:

(1) Recent decisions were not justified on the basis of a consolidated view from science and other knowledge holders and, even more worryingly, some of these decisions were based on **misinformation** (see the [open letter signed by 6000 scientists](#)) and on **targeted data collection** not complying with the Better Regulation Guidelines on stakeholder consultation (see [inquiry opened by the European Ombudsman](#)).

(2) These decisions appear to be **heavily influenced by the particular interests** of specific groups and corporations within a narrow segment of society, some of which were expressed through violent and undemocratic ways. Moreover, they conflict even with their own aims as defined by decision makers, since, according to the best available science, they will jeopardise the resilience of farming and fisheries, and risk our common future including the livelihoods of the same stakeholders they claim to support.

(3) Finally, as a global leader in climate, biodiversity and environmental legislation, the **EU is now sending highly regrettable and contradictory signals to the rest of the world**. We regret observing the EU's lack of real commitment in returning to the safe operating space for humanity.

What needs to be done?

We welcome the final approval on 18 August 2024 of the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), and President Von der Leyen's expression of commitment to make the NRR a success. Members of the scientific community stand ready to support the EU and the Member States in successfully implementing this important new regulation. We are encouraged by the clear signal placed by the European Council in rejecting the Parliament's proposed amendments of the EUDR, thereby aligning with science and acknowledging Europe's global role and

responsibility. We further welcome the recommendations made in the Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture and President Von der Leyen's endorsement of the outcomes - with the hope that this will be upheld and reflected in swift policy action. **However, with the new Commission signalling a drastic shift to the Green Deal's implementation, away from sustainability principles, we urge setting the ambition back on a truly transformative pathway by:**

1) Revoking the latest contested decisions. As members of the scientific community, we stand ready to provide more consolidated consensus views to improve them. We urge the Commission to take back the recent changes described above with regards to the RES and CAP, given the risks of enhancing environmental problems and health hazards. In the longer term, we call the Commission to consider a significant and **ambitious reform of the CAP**, to improve its coherence with its own objectives as well as with the Green Deal (see also [ECA report](#)). We also urge the new Commission to **place the SUR back on the table**, and to avoid further dilution of environmental regulations and policies, including the Nitrate Directive, the Deforestation Regulation, the Habitats Directive and the Bern Convention.

2) Setting a clear and ambitious agenda for environmental protection and the Green Deal for the post-election period. The agenda should align with the science of the Earth's planetary boundaries and **acknowledge Europe's disproportionate contribution to the global crises**. We must take environmental issues with utmost seriousness, as they pose severe and growing threats to society and the long-term survival of our civilization.

3) Developing an EU-wide coordinated action plan to address **Europe's overproduction of animal products**, leading to high emissions of nitrogen and methane, manure and other pollutants, as well as land-use pressures affecting both human health and ecosystems.

4) Further developing and **using the existing Science-for-Policy ecosystem** (initiated by the European Commission) such as the Scientific Advice Mechanism or the EC Knowledge Center for Biodiversity and its future Science Service for Biodiversity. Not only the scientific community, but also policymakers and society, would all benefit from a more coherent science-policy interface, at the EU and national levels, to ensure effective and timely use of the expertise we can contribute.

Finally, **we call on citizens, civil society organisations and political parties to support responsible policymaking** that secures a safe future within Earth's planetary boundaries, promoting sustainability and resilience, while upholding the socio-economic foundation for all.

Sincerely,

the authors, as well as all signatory bodies and individuals
(see list of signatories below)

Signatory bodies:

1. The Society for Conservation Biology - Europe Region
2. The Society for Ecological Restoration Europe
3. Ecological Society of Germany, Austria, and Switzerland
4. Netherlands Ecological Research Network
5. Ecosystem Services Partnership – European chapter
6. Society of Wetland Scientists – Europe Chapter
7. Austrian Biodiversity Council of the Austrian Biodiversity Network
8. Hungarian Ecological Society
9. Czech Society for Ecology
10. Society for Tropical Ecology
11. Austrian Zoological-Botanical Society
12. Italian Society for Evolutionary Biology
13. Eurasian Dry Grassland Group EDGG
14. Societas Europaea Herpetologica (SEH)
15. International Association for Landscape Ecology - German Chapter
16. International Union for Agroforestry (IUAF)
17. IAVS Working Group European Vegetation Survey
18. Researchers' Desk
19. Amsterdam institute for life Environment (Faculty of Science, VU)
20. French-speaking Society for Ecological Economics (SoFEE – Société Francophone d'Economie Ecologique)
21. Scientists for Future (Interdisciplinary Scientific Panel)
22. Alternet
23. The French Society of Astronomy and Astrophysics (SF2A)
24. Austrian Mycological Society
25. Italian Society of Vegetation Science (SISV)
26. CETAF, the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities
27. French Society for Ecology and Evolution (SFE²)
28. Oikos Finland
29. Spanish Association for Terrestrial Ecology (AEET)
30. Ethologische Gesellschaft e.V.
31. Vlinderstichting / Dutch Butterfly Conservation

Open Letter: scientists urge EU policymakers to reinstate the Green Deal
12.2.2025

Österreichische
Mykologische
Gesellschaft

aeet
ASOCIACIÓN
ESPAÑOLA DE
ECOLOGÍA
TERRESTRE

Details on signatory bodies:

[The Society for Conservation Biology - Europe Region](#) is dedicated to facilitating, promoting, and advancing the scientific study and conservation of biological diversity.

[The Society for Ecological Restoration Europe](#) is the network that advances the science, practice, and policy of ecological restoration to sustain biodiversity, improve resilience in a changing climate, and re-establish an ecologically healthy relationship between nature and culture.

The [Ecological Society of Germany, , Austria, and Switzerland](#) (GfÖ - Gesellschaft für Ökologie e.V.) is dedicated to ecology in science and practice. Its membership centres in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. The Society supports ecological research and training, and promotes the exchange of ecologists in academic institutions, public administration and the private sector by organising annual meetings and working groups.

[The Netherlands Ecological Research Network \(NERN\)](#) is the network of professional ecologists in the Netherlands where all universities and research institutes that have an ecology program participate.

[Ecosystem Services Partnership \(ESP\) – European region](#). ESP is a global network, connecting over 3.500 people, to connect ecosystem services scientists, practitioners, stakeholders, and policymakers at local, national, regional, and global scales. ESP aims to enhance communication, coordination and cooperation, and to build a strong network of individuals and organisations working on ecosystem services.

The [Society of Wetland Scientists \(SWS\) – Europe Chapter](#). SWS works to promote best practices in wetland research, education, conservation, preservation, restoration, and management. SWS has over 3,000 members in more than 60 countries.

The [Czech Society for Ecology \(CSPE\)](#) is a professional society bringing together scientific, scientific-pedagogical and professional workers, students and other persons dealing with ecology. CSPE participate in the comprehensive, complex and systematic development of ecological disciplines, and in the promotion and implementation of research results, in nature protection and landscapes and expert activities in Central Europe.

Members of the [Austrian Biodiversity Council](#) of the [Austrian Biodiversity Network](#) are researchers from various disciplines as well as experts in the fields of biodiversity, landscape design and nature conservation. The Austrian Biodiversity Network sees itself as an open, interdisciplinary community encompassing a wide range of specialist disciplines and transdisciplinary for science, politics, administration, business, NGOs and civil society. The common goal is to strengthen biodiversity and its ecosystem services in Austria.

[Hungarian Ecological Society](#) is an NGO of Hungarian ecologists with 145 members. Its main tasks are to organise scientific conferences, meetings, courses, summer schools, to support ecological research, as well as to represent the opinion of ecologists for the society.

The **Spanish Association for Terrestrial Ecology (AEET)** is an association that brings together nearly 1000 researchers in ecology from all the university centres and Public Research Institutions in Spain. The purpose of the AEET is to foster research in Ecology, to raise awareness and encourage public participation in matters of environmental interest and to promote the responsible application of Ecological knowledge.

The [Society for Tropical Ecology](#) (Gesellschaft für Tropenökologie e.V., GTÖ) promotes and communicates new and emerging knowledge among tropical ecologists and conservationists to advance the understanding of tropical ecosystems and their protection. GTÖ's goal is to connect students and academics with an interest in tropical ecology from around the world to understand and preserve the biodiversity and functions of tropical ecosystems. GTÖ is currently Europe's largest scientific association for tropical ecological research.

[Austrian Zoological-Botanical Society](#) ("Zoologisch-Botanische Gesellschaft in Österreich"; ZooBot) supports nature conservation and science (especially organismic biology, ecology, and research on biodiversity). Thus it offers a platform for scientists, students, teachers at universities as well as other educational institutions, museum curators as well as interested laymen, cooperating with many other associations and institutions. The society is one of the longest existing in Austria, and has around 400 members.

The **Italian Society for Evolutionary Biology (SIBE)** is a non-profit scientific association whose main missions are to promote the correct dissemination of knowledge related to biological evolution; to promote evolutionary studies, particularly favouring young researchers; to stimulate the dialogue with foreign colleagues; to strengthen scientific relations between Italian evolutionary biologists active worldwide.

The [Eurasian Dry Grassland Group](#) (EDGG) is a network of researchers and conservationists interested in Palaearctic natural and semi-natural grasslands. It was established in 2008 and is a working group of the International Association for Vegetation Science and ([IAVS](#)) and a member of the European Forum for Nature Conservation and Pastoralism ([EFNCP](#)).

The **Societas Europaea Herpetologica (SEH)**, founded in 1979, is a society of nearly 400 members (professional and non-professional herpetologists) from European and other countries. SEH publishes a quarterly peer-reviewed journal Amphibia-Reptilia and an online journal Herpetology Notes. Biannually the European Congress of Herpetology is organised by members of the society.

The **International Association for Landscape Ecology - German Chapter (IALE-D)** connects landscape researchers, planners and other interested parties to promote the scientifically and planning-based design of human-environment relationships. The association is committed to the scientific foundations of landscape research and sustainable landscape management, their application in practice, and the professional communication of landscape-ecological issues.

The **International Union for Agroforestry (IUAF)** is a network of members sharing a common interest in agroforestry; it is an international platform for individuals and institutions to share agroforestry practices and research. Our goal is the worldwide adoption of agroforestry

practices by governments, policymakers, regulators, and farmers as together we can contribute to more sustainable agriculture and help our planet. IUAF was created at the World Congress on Agroforestry in Montpellier in 2019 with the support of the Czech Republic.

[European Vegetation Survey \(EVS\)](#) is a Working Group of the **International Association for Vegetation Science (IAVS)**, uniting plant ecologists interested in vegetation survey and classification in Europe and beyond.

[Researchers' Desk \(RD\)](#) is a Swedish non-profit organization that unites researchers and civil society in pursuit of knowledge-based solutions to the ongoing climate and biodiversity crisis. RD creates meeting places between the general public and experts where knowledge, insights, and scientific facts are shared. RD is independent and politically non-partisan. Members of RD are deeply concerned about climate change, and their concern is based on science.

The **Amsterdam institute for life Environment** (Faculty of Science, VU - **A-LIFE-VU**) deepens the understanding of the relationships between life and its environment through cutting-edge, curiosity-fuelled research. The department explores the connections between properties and emergent behaviours across diverse scales, from molecular to ecological, including human populations. Its goal is to inspire students and leverage its expertise to advance sustainability and support healthy living.

Founded in 2023, **SoFEE (French-speaking Society for Ecological Economics)** brings together researchers, professors, students, non-academic professionals and associations working to promote ecological economics in science, policy and education. Our activities focus on supporting and disseminating ideas, results, approaches and initiatives aimed at transforming the economy outside the dominant framework of green growth, in order to implement principles of strong sustainability and environmental justice.

[Scientists for Future \(Interdisciplinary Scientific Panel\)](#) supports the global climate movement by providing facts and materials based on reliable and accepted scientific data to activists, politicians, decision-makers, educators and the general public. It is an independent and voluntary collective of scientists, researchers and academics from all kinds of disciplines, united by the deep concern for a shared future.

[Alternet](#) is the network of leading institutes from 21 European countries that share the goal of integrating their research capability to assess changes in biodiversity, analyse the effect of those changes on ecosystem services and inform the public and policymakers about this at a European scale.

The **French Society of Astronomy and Astrophysics** (Société Française d'Astronomie et d'astrophysique; **SF2A**) aims to contribute to the development and influence of astronomy in France and to involve all astronomy professionals working towards this same objective. SF2A plays a very important and unique role in the life of the French astronomical community with several actions, among which: organizing the Annual French Astronomical Days, awarding of Young Researcher and Thesis prizes; and distributing a weekly newsletter. Also, the SF2A is an affiliated society of the European Astronomical Society and as such participates in discussions between European countries regarding the organization of astronomy in Europe. The SF2A is the sole interlocutor between the French community and the IAU. Finally, the SF2A carries out numerous actions to strengthen the link between science and society, by supporting outreach events, organizing public conferences, organizing school prizes etc.

The **Austrian Mycological Society (ÖMG)** is a network of professional and amateur mycologists and is open to all interested people. Universities, research institutes and citizen scientists representing practical and scientific mycology and having a deep interest in fungi, including systematics, distribution, ecology and conservation, cooperate.

The **Italian Society of Vegetation Science (SISV)** was founded in 2006 as a continuation of the Italian Society of Phytosociology (S.I.Fs., established 1964). SISV promotes and supports research on vegetation and habitats, fosters collaboration between researchers at national and international level, cooperates with institutions involved in land management and organises scientific symposia, conferences, excursions, courses and internships. It oversees the publication of the journal *Plant Sociology* (soon to be *Vegetation Ecology and Diversity*), and manages the vegetation database *VegItaly*. SISV currently has over 200 members.

CETAF, the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities is a unique scientific organisation of more than 80 institutions across 27 countries in Europe. CETAF envisions a world where natural science collections and knowledge of biodiversity and geodiversity drive a sustainable future for nature and society. We bring together natural sciences and natural history museums, botanical gardens and research centres in a joint effort to promote research in taxonomy and systematics in Europe by facilitating expert collaboration and knowledge sharing among its member institutions, advocating for the value of collection-based research, and enhancing the accessibility, use, and impact of natural science collections.

French Society for Ecology and Evolution (SFE²) aims to promote the development, integration and sharing within the Society as a whole of knowledge in the sciences of ecology and evolution in France.

Oikos Finland is the ecological society of Finland bringing together researchers in the field of ecology and evolutionary biology.

The **Spanish Association for Terrestrial Ecology (Asociación Española de Ecología Terrestre, AEET)** is a scientific society dedicated to advancing research, education, and conservation in terrestrial ecology in Spain. It promotes collaboration among ecologists, dissemination of ecological knowledge, and the application of ecological science to address environmental challenges.

[The Ethologische Gesellschaft e.V.](#) is a non-profit organisation, founded with the aim of supporting behavioural research in science and teaching. It was founded on 10 October 1978 in Basel (Switzerland). The society now has about 400 members, most of whom are from German-speaking countries (Austria, Germany, Switzerland) and the Netherlands.

De **Vlinderstichting / Dutch Butterfly Conservation** works on conserving, restoring and developing nature with the focus on butterflies, moths and dragonflies. We carry out research and give advice to nature conservation practitioners as well as policy makers. We strongly support citizen science and use the data to determine distribution and population trends in the Netherlands as well as at a European scale. Whenever possible, Dutch Butterfly Conservation works in partnership with other data-collecting organizations, amongst others as a partner of Butterfly Conservation Europe (BCE).

List of individual signatories (12.02.2025)

Disclaimer: while all efforts were made to assure that all signatories are proven scientists, errors may still occur. Should you identify that someone was erroneously listed, or if you signed but your name is missing, please inform the authors.

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1263. Italy, Bojana Stojanova, University of Naples Federico II
1264. Italy, Francesca De Filippis, University of Naples Federico II
1265. Italy, Simonetta Frascchetti, University of Naples Federico II
1266. Italy, Alberto LaNZAVECCHIA, University of Padova
1267. Italy, Alessandro Incarbona, University of Palermo

1268. Italy, Luigi Badalucco, University of Palermo
1269. Italy, Alessandro Petraglia, University of Parma
1270. Italy, ANDREA MONDONI, University of Pavia
1271. Italy, Lino Ometto, University of Pavia
1272. Italy, Mauro Capestro, University of Pavia
1273. Italy, Silvia Assini, University of Pavia
1274. Italy, Simone Orsenigo, University of Pavia
1275. Italy, Marco Cucco, University of Piemonte Orientale
1276. Italy, Simone D'Alessandro, University of Pisa
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1278. Italy, Michele Solca, University of Salento
1279. Italy, Luigi De Bellis, University of Salento
1280. Italy, Luigi Musco, University of Salento
1281. Italy, Anna Lisa Piccinelli, University of Salerno
1282. Italy, Erica Nocerino, University of Sassari
1283. Italy, Giulia Ceccherelli, University of Sassari
1284. Italy, Massimo Scandura, University of Sassari
1285. Italy, Emanuele Fanfarillo, University of Siena
1286. Italy, Gianmaria Bonari, University of Siena
1287. Italy, Massimo Nepi, University of Siena
1288. Italy, Chiara Cortinovia, University of Trento
1289. Italy, Davide Geneletti, University of Trento
1290. Italy, Lia Laporta, University of Trento
1291. Italy, Michael Matiu, University of Trento
1292. Italy, Alexander Eperon, University of Trento
1293. Italy, Annalisa Falace, University of Trieste, Dept Life Sciences
1294. Italy, Piero Belletti, University of Turin
1295. Italy, ELENA BARNI, University of Turin
1296. Italy, Giulia Caneva, University Roma Tre
1297. Italy, Carla Lambertini, University of Milan
1298. Italy, James Karimi, wwf
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1302. Italy, Sergio Noce, CMCC Foundation
1303. Italy, Fantina Madricarso, CNR
1304. Italy, Madara Melnika, EUI
1305. Italy, Federico Voltolini, Eurac Research
1306. Italy, Giacomo Bertoldi, Eurac Research
1307. Italy, Sonja Gantioler, Eurac Research
1308. Italy, Andreas Hilpold, Eurac Research, Institute for Alpine Environment
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1311. Italy, Antonio Donateo, Italian National Research Council (CNR)
1312. Italy, Javier Babi Almenar, Politecnico di Milano
1313. Italy, maria chiara pastore, politecnico di milano
1314. Italy, Enrico Mezzacapo, Sant'Anna school of advanced studies
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1330. Italy, M. Susana Orta-Ortiz, University of Trento
1331. Italy, Enrico Caprio, University of Turin
1332. Italy, Gianluca Piovesan, University of Tuscia
1333. Italy, Iduna Arduini, University of Pisa
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1349. Netherlands, Guusje Koorneef, NIOO-KNAW
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- 1364. Netherlands, Anne Rietveld, Bioversity International
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- 1366. Netherlands, Herman van Dam, Consultancy for Water and Nature
- 1367. Netherlands, Inês Vicente, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development - Utrecht University
- 1368. Netherlands, Rense Haveman, De Ronde & Haveman
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- 1386. Netherlands, Henrik Barmentlo, Leiden University
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1471. Netherlands, Frank Berendse, Utrecht University
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1530. Netherlands, Leopold Nagelkerke, Wageningen University
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1533. Netherlands, Madelon Lohbeck, Wageningen University
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1539. Netherlands, Nico van den Brink, Wageningen University

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1544. Netherlands, Pieter Zuidema, Wageningen University
1545. Netherlands, Rick Buesink, Wageningen University
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1559. Netherlands, Cajo ter Braak, Wageningen University & Research
1560. Netherlands, Edgar van der Grift, Wageningen University & Research
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1605. Netherlands, Inge van de Wiel, WUR
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1692. Other, Pablo Evia, CATIE
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1863. Spain, Francisco Pugnaire, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
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1866. Spain, Alba Anadon-Rosell, CREAM
1867. Spain, Enrique Doblaz, CREAM
1868. Spain, Joan Maso, CREAM
1869. Spain, Joan Pino, CREAM
1870. Spain, Jordi Bosch, CREAM
1871. Spain, Jordi Catalan, CREAM
1872. Spain, Mercedes Ibañez Raffaele, CREAM
1873. Spain, Pilar Andrés, CREAM
1874. Spain, Roxanne Leberger, CREAM
1875. Spain, Sara Marañón Jiménez, CREAM
1876. Spain, Tristan Bakx, CREAM
1877. Spain, Vicenç Carabassa, CREAM
1878. Spain, Jordi Martínez-Vilalta, CREAM - Autonomous Univ. Barcelona
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1880. Spain, Carlos Alonso, CSIC
1881. Spain, Cristina Armas, CSIC
1882. Spain, Diego Gil, CSIC
1883. Spain, Eduardo Aguilera, CSIC
1884. Spain, Ignacio de la Riva, CSIC
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2041. Spain, Guille Peguero, University of Barcelona
2042. Spain, Juan Moles, University of Barcelona
2043. Spain, Pau Colom, University of Barcelona
2044. Spain, Yolanda Melero, University of Barcelona
2045. Spain, Noemi Luna Carmeno, University of Barcelona
2046. Spain, María Belén Hinojosa Centeno, University of Castilla-La Mancha
2047. Spain, Federico Fernández-González, University of Castilla-La Mancha
2048. Spain, Nicolas Valiente, University of Castilla-La Mancha
2049. Spain, Pablo Ferrandis, University of Castilla-La Mancha
2050. Spain, María Suárez Muñoz, University of Cordoba
2051. Spain, ROLANDO Rodriguez-Munoz, University of Exeter
2052. Spain, Emili García-Berthou, University of Girona
2053. Spain, José Padiá, University of Granada
2054. Spain, Magdalena Ruiz-Rodríguez, University of Granada
2055. Spain, Marcos Moleón Paiz, University of Granada
2056. Spain, Regino Zamora, University of Granada
2057. Spain, SERGIO ARANDA BARRANCO, University of Granada
2058. Spain, Tomás Pérez-Contreras, University of Granada
2059. Spain, Nicolas OLEA, University of Granada. Granada
2060. Spain, F. Javier Jiménez Nieva, University of Huelva
2061. Spain, Carlos Salazar-Mendías, University of Jaén
2062. Spain, Ana Ruiz-Navarro, University of Murcia
2063. Spain, Hugo Robles, University of Oviedo
2064. Spain, DANIEL GARCÍA, University of Oviedo
2065. Spain, Enrique González-Bernardo, University of Oviedo, University of Granada
2066. Spain, Francisco Navarro Rosales, University of Oxford
2067. Spain, Blanca Rojas, University of Salamanca
2068. Spain, Javier Quinteiro, University of Santiago de Compostela
2069. Spain, Irene Mendoza, University of Sevilla
2070. Spain, Luis Matías, University of Seville
2071. Spain, María Cruz Díaz Barradas, University of Seville
2072. Spain, Marta Rueda, University of Seville
2073. Spain, Damià Gomis, University of the Balearic Islands
2074. Spain, Aitor Larrañaga, University of the Basque Country
2075. Spain, Arantza Aldezabal, University of the Basque Country
2076. Spain, Arturo Elosegi, University of the Basque Country
2077. Spain, Maialen Sistiaga, University of the Basque Country
2078. Spain, Oihana Barrutia, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)
2079. Spain, Alicia García, University of Valencia
2080. Spain, Jesús Tomás Aguirre, University of Valencia
2081. Spain, Juan Antonio Raga Esteve, University of Valencia

2082. Spain, Manuel Serra, University of Valencia
2083. Spain, Maria J I Briones, University of Vigo
2084. Spain, Raquel Juan Ovejero, University of Vigo
2085. Spain, José Enrique Pérez Rodríguez, University of Vigo
2086. Spain, Blanca Ivañez-Ballesteros, University of Würzburg
2087. Spain, Antonio Gallardo, University Pablo de Olavide
2088. Spain, Cayetano Gutiérrez Cánovas, University Rey Juan Carlos
2089. Spain, David García de León Hernández, Ayuntamiento de Mejorada del Campo
2090. Spain, Daniel Montoya, Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3)
2091. Spain, Jose Manuel Alvarez Martinez, Biodiversity Research Institute, IMIB | University of Oviedo-CSIC-Principality of Asturias
2092. Spain, Bruno Moreira, Centro de Investigaciones sobre Desertificación (CIDE), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
2093. Spain, Miguel Cabanellas-Reboredo, Centro Oceanográfico de Illes Balears (COB-IEO), CSIC. Balearic Islands, Spain
2094. Spain, María Mar Sánchez-Montoya, Complutense University of Madrid
2095. Spain, Arnald Marcer, CREAM
2096. Spain, Dani Villero Pi, CREAM
2097. Spain, Marcos Fernández Martínez, CREAM
2098. Spain, Maria Blasi, CREAM
2099. Spain, Laura Hernandez Mateo, CSIC
2100. Spain, Marta Coll, CSIC
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2103. Spain, Isabel Salado, EBD-CSIC
2104. Spain, Zulima Tablado, EBD-CSIC
2105. Spain, Lia Alves, IDIAP Jordi Gol
2106. Spain, Patricia Reglero, Instituto Español de Oceanografía-CSIC
2107. Spain, Iker Irisarri, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales
2108. Spain, Ana Benítez López, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN-CSIC)
2109. Spain, Carlos Alonso-Alvarez, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN-CSIC)
2110. Spain, Gema Escribano Ávila, Tragsatec, Biodiversity and Protected Areas Department
2111. Spain, Maria José Fernández Alonso, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid
2112. Spain, Rodrigo Megía Palma, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)
2113. Spain, Beatriz Duguy Pedra, Universidad de Barcelona
2114. Spain, Raul de la Mata Pombo, Universidad de Extremadura
2115. Spain, Zebensui Morales-Reyes, Universidad de La Laguna
2116. Spain, Johannes Langemeyer, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
2117. Spain, Carla Olmo, Universitat de Girona
2118. Spain, Jon Morant Etxebarria, University of Alicante
2119. Spain, Ignacio Maeso, University of Barcelona
2120. Spain, Rocío López-Orozco, University of Córdoba
2121. Spain, Lourdes Morillas, University of Seville
2122. Spain, Guillem Xavier Pons, University of the Balearic Islands
2123. Spain, Ana Iglesias, UPM
2124. Sweden, Chenyu Jin, Centre for Palaeogenetics

2125. Sweden, Frances Sprei, Chalmers University of Technology
2126. Sweden, U. Martin Persson, Chalmers University of Technology
2127. Sweden, Mara Mennuni, Karolinska Institutet
2128. Sweden, Maganizo Nyasulu, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2129. Sweden, Alexandra McFadden, Stockholm University
2130. Sweden, Kevin Noone, Stockholm University
2131. Sweden, David Andersson, Chalmers
2132. Sweden, Timon Renzelmann, Chalmers
2133. Sweden, Malaika Yanou, Chalmers University of Technology
2134. Sweden, Yuan Liao, Chalmers University of Technology
2135. Sweden, Angelica Wågström, Chalmers University of Technology
2136. Sweden, Hanna Ek Fälth, Chalmers University of Technology
2137. Sweden, Viviane Baladi, CNRS (retired)
2138. Sweden, Fabian Lenhard, Department of Clinical Neuroscience, Karolinska Institutet
2139. Sweden, Fede Berckx, Department of Crop Production Ecology
2140. Sweden, Associate professor Cecilia Kullberg, Dept of Zoology, Stockholm University
2141. Sweden, Bengt Gunnar Jonsson, Dept. of Natural Science, Design and Sustainable Development, Mid Sweden University, Sundsvall
2142. Sweden, EWDA (through Chair Erik Ågren) European section of the Wildlife Disease Association, European section of the Wildlife Disease Association, EWDA
2143. Sweden, Jane Ekstam, Høgskolen i Østfold, Norway
2144. Sweden, Ewa Orlikowska, Karlstad University
2145. Sweden, Simon Perrin, Karolinska Institute
2146. Sweden, Stefan Nobel, Karolinska Institutet
2147. Sweden, Ann Liljas, Karolinska Institutet
2148. Sweden, Associate Professor Bo Franzén, Karolinska Institutet
2149. Sweden, Elles de Schipper, Karolinska Institutet
2150. Sweden, Linda Sturesson Stabel, Karolinska Institutet
2151. Sweden, Marion Humbert, Karolinska Institutet
2152. Sweden, Rebecca Andersson, Karolinska Institutet
2153. Sweden, Tove Wahlund, Karolinska institutet
2154. Sweden, Adjunct Sara Widén, Karolinska Institutet
2155. Sweden, Anne-Kathrin Peters, KTH Royal Institute of Technology
2156. Sweden, Göran Finnveden, KTH Royal Institute of Technology
2157. Sweden, Minna Laurell Thorslund, KTH Royal Institute of Technology
2158. Sweden, Glenn Bark, Luleå University of Technology
2159. Sweden, Prof emer Cecilia Emanuelsson, Lund University
2160. Sweden, Henner Busch, Lund University
2161. Sweden, Jennifer Hinton, Lund University
2162. Sweden, Roberto García-Roa, Lund University
2163. Sweden, Tomas Persson, Lund University
2164. Sweden, Tullia Jack, Lund University
2165. Sweden, Assoc. Prof. Carolin Zorell, Örebro University
2166. Sweden, Associate Prof. Malin Ah-king, Örebro University
2167. Sweden, Shruti Kashyap, Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences
2168. Sweden, Magnuz Engardt, SMHI
2169. Sweden, Ali Hajighasemi, Södertörn University
2170. Sweden, Associate Professor Veronica Svärd, Södertörn University

2171. Sweden, PhD Candidate Per Bolund, Stockholm Resilience Center at Stockholm University
2172. Sweden, Giorgio Parlato, Stockholm Resilience Center, Stockholm University
2173. Sweden, Therese Sivertsson, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2174. Sweden, Bianca Voicu, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2175. Sweden, Lisa Deutsch, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2176. Sweden, Sofia Maniatakou, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2177. Sweden, Juan Rocha, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2178. Sweden, Line Gordon, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2179. Sweden, Nielja Knecht, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2180. Sweden, Thorsten Blenckner, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2181. Sweden, Romi Lotcheris, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2182. Sweden, Miriam Huitric, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2183. Sweden, Beatrice Crona, Stockholm University
2184. Sweden, Caroline Greiser, Stockholm University
2185. Sweden, Lennart Winkler, Stockholm University
2186. Sweden, Lisa Dellmuth, Stockholm University
2187. Sweden, Maria Mancilla Garcia, Stockholm University
2188. Sweden, Miriam Kuspiel, Stockholm University
2189. Sweden, Paul Glantz, Stockholm University
2190. Sweden, Thibault Caron, Stockholm University
2191. Sweden, Thomas Elmqvist, Stockholm University
2192. Sweden, Anna Brødsgaard Shoshan, Stockholm University
2193. Sweden, Ingo Müller, Stockholm University
2194. Sweden, Julie Bommerlund, Stockholm University
2195. Sweden, Monique Smith, Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet
2196. Sweden, Johannes Bergsten, Swedish Museum of Natural History
2197. Sweden, Valentina Peona, Swedish Natural History Museum
2198. Sweden, Chloe MacLaren, Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU)
2199. Sweden, Kristine Koch, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2200. Sweden, Alwin Hardenbol, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2201. Sweden, Amelia Mutter, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2202. Sweden, Cassandra Vogel, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2203. Sweden, Cecilia Lalander, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2204. Sweden, Cecilia Palmborg, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2205. Sweden, Chloé Raderschall, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2206. Sweden, Associate professor Elin Rööös, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2207. Sweden, Erik Öckinger, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2208. Sweden, Flora Hajdu, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2209. Sweden, Jeannette Eggers, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2210. Sweden, Johanna Spångberg, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2211. Sweden, Margaux Boeraeve, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2212. Sweden, Maria Viketoft, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2213. Sweden, Max Lindmark, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2214. Sweden, Michael Bertram, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2215. Sweden, Patrik Oskarsson, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2216. Sweden, Rasmus Einarsson, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2217. Sweden, Simon Kärverno, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

2218. Sweden, Svenja Horstmann, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2219. Sweden, Stephanie Leder-Büttner, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)
2220. Sweden, Max Troell, The Beijer Institute of Ecological Economics
2221. Sweden, Louis Delannoy, The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences
2222. Sweden, Mairon Bastos Lima, The Stockholm Environment Institute
2223. Sweden, Johanna Yourstone, University of Aberdeen
2224. Sweden, Per Ribbing, Uppsala University
2225. Sweden, Fouad El Gohary, Uppsala University
2226. Sweden, Kristina Boréus, Uppsala University
2227. Sweden, Jacqueline Hoppenreijts, Karlstad University
2228. Sweden, Ola Kalén, SMHI
2229. Sweden, Rachel Mazac, Stockholm Resilience Centre
2230. Sweden, Garry Peterson, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2231. Sweden, Ingo Fetzer, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
2232. Sweden, Thomas Hahn, Stockholm University
2233. Sweden, Göran Ågren, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2234. Sweden, Paul Kardol, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
2235. Sweden, María Trinidad Torres García, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)
2236. Sweden, Bengt Å Carlsson, Uppsala University
2237. United Kingdom, Devin Ward, Springer Nature
2238. United Kingdom, Martin Warren, Butterfly Conservation Europe
2239. United Kingdom, Emma Burnett, CAWR
2240. United Kingdom, Rupert Read, Climate Majority Project
2241. United Kingdom, Mr. Alex Caruana, Department of Biology, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK
2242. United Kingdom, Mariana Carvalho, Fauna and Flora
2243. United Kingdom, Giel Ton, Institute of Development Studies
2244. United Kingdom, Fred Basso, London School of Economics
2245. United Kingdom, Matti Leponiemi, Royal Holloway University of London
2246. United Kingdom, Senior Research Fellow Richard Scott, Society for Ecological Restoration Europe
2247. United Kingdom, Joseph Eastoe, UCL
2248. United Kingdom, James Bullock, UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
2249. United Kingdom, Markus Wagner, UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
2250. United Kingdom, NaDINE Mitschunas, UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
2251. United Kingdom, Asun Rodríguez-Uña, University of Cambridge
2252. United Kingdom, Mr Chris Short, University of Gloucestershire
2253. United Kingdom, Mark Schuerch, University of Lincoln
2254. United Kingdom, László Demeter, University of Nottingham, School of Geography
2255. United Kingdom, David Moreno Mateos, University of Oxford
2256. United Kingdom, Marina Morente Diaz, University of Oxford
2257. United Kingdom, Niak Sian Koh, University of Oxford
2258. United Kingdom, Ms. Kim Ross, University of Plymouth
2259. United Kingdom, Anne Magurran, University of St Andrews
2260. United Kingdom, Feja Lesniewska, University of Surrey
2261. United Kingdom, M.Res. Gabrielle Flinn, University of York
2262. United Kingdom, Gordon Madamombe, Coventry University

Selected links to relevant publications and open letters by scientists:

On the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP):

- Leopoldina (2020): Biodiversity and Management of Agricultural Landscapes, Published by the German National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina, Halle/Saale. <https://bit.ly/3RVnXtW>
- WBAE (2019): Designing an effective agri-environment-climate policy as part of the post-2020 EU Common Agricultural Policy, Statement of the Scientific Board for Food and Environmental Policy (WBAE) at the Federal Ministry for Food and Agriculture, Berlin. <https://bit.ly/4aDojvb>
- WBAE (2018): For an EU Common Agricultural Policy serving the public good after 2020: Fundamental questions and recommendations, Statement of the Scientific Board for Food and Environmental Policy (WBAE) at the Federal Ministry for Food and Agriculture, Berlin. <https://bit.ly/4bKtLOk>
- Díaz et al. (2021). Environmental objectives of Spanish agriculture: Scientific guidelines for their effective implementation under the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2030. *Ardeola*, 68(2), 445-460. <https://doi.org/10.13157/arla.68.2.2021.fo1>
- Pe'er et al. (2020): Action needed for the EU Common Agricultural Policy to address sustainability challenges, *People and Nature* 2 (2): 305-316. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10080>
- Pe'er et al. (2022): How can the European Common Agricultural Policy help halt biodiversity loss? Recommendations by over 300 experts, *Conservation Letters* 15 (6): e12901. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12901>
- Morales et al. (2022). Protect European green agricultural policies for future food security. *Communications earth & environment*, 3(1), 217. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00550-2>
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- Pardo et al. (2020) To what extent does the European Common Agricultural Policy affect key landscape determinants of biodiversity? *Environmental Science & Policy* 114: 595-605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.09.023>
- Concepción et al. (2020). Optimizing biodiversity gain of European agriculture through regional targeting and adaptive management of conservation tools. *Biological Conservation* 241: 108384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2019.108384>

On NRL and SUR:

- Pe'er et al. (2023) Scientists support the EU's Green Deal and reject the unjustified argumentation against the Sustainable Use Regulation and the Nature Restoration Law. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8128624> - [signed by 6000 scientists](#)

On EU contribution to the loss of old-growth forests in Europe and deforestation elsewhere:

- Zinggerebe et al. (2024), [Prioritizing partners and products for the sustainability of the EU's agri-food trade.](#)

- Mikoláš et al. (2023). [Protect old-growth forests in Europe now](#). Science, 380(6644), 466-466.
- Curtis, P. G., Slay, C. M., Harris, N. L., Tyukavina, A., & Hansen, M. C. (2018). Classifying drivers of global forest loss. Science, 361(6407), 1108-1111. DOI: 10.1126/science.aau3445

On the Nature Restoration Law (NRL):

- Hering et al. (2023), Securing success for the Nature Restoration Law. Science 382, 1248-1250. DOI: [10.1126/science.adk1658](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adk1658); [Open Access link](#)
- SER Europe Legal Working Group (2024). 10 legal reasons to vote in favour of the EU Nature Restoration Law. <https://serchapter2018.wpenginepowered.com/europe/files/2024/03/10-Legal-Reasons-to-vote-YES-for-NRL-1.pdf>
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- Chapron G. et al.(2023). European Commission may gut wolf protection. Science, 382(6668), 275-275.
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- Kati et al. 2023. The overlooked threat of land take from wind energy infrastructures: Quantification, drivers and policy gaps. Journal of Environmental Management 348, 119340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.119340>
- Serrano et al. 2020. Renewables in Spain, threaten biodiversity. Science 370, 1282–1283. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abf6509>.
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- Garcia-Gonzalez, F., Ripple, W. J. & Malo, A. F. 2024. Scientists' warning to humanity for long-term planetary thinking on biodiversity and humankind preservation, a cosmic perspective. BioScience 74, 82-85. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biad108>.

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- Schebesta, H. & J.J.L. Candel (2020): Game-changing potential of the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy. Nat Food 1, 586–588. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-020-00166-9>
- Durá-Alemañ et al. (2023) Climate change and energy crisis drive an unprecedented EU environmental law regression. Conservation Letters 16:e12958 <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12958>